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Editor

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**DEPARTMENT OF WEST ASIAN
AND NORTH AFRICAN STUDIES
ALIGARH MUSLIM UNIVERSITY
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JOURNAL OF WEST ASIAN STUDIES

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EDITORIAL

It gives me immense pleasure to present before you the volume thirty five of the Journal of West Asian Studies. Journal of West Asian Studies is an annual publication of the Department of West Asian Studies published uninterrupted since last thirty five years. It is concerned with the various cultural, economic, historical political and social issues, both contemporary and past of the West Asian region. Continuous efforts have been made to improve the quality of the Journal. For the articles to be accepted for publication original contribution, systematic and scientific methodology, the scholarly rigour and contribution to the existing stock of knowledge certified by the referees have been the sole criteria for the acceptance of papers for publication. This volume consists of 18 papers concerned with the divergent issues of the region which is termed as West Asia.

The first paper in this volume by Girijesh Pant and Vrushal Ghoble deals with an important issue which is Saudi Arabia's political economy of geo-economic shift. It says that the socioeconomic pressures have triggered the laying of foundations of knowledge economy. It expects generation of participatory phenomenon resulting in some devolution of power. The second paper by Muhammad Azhar discusses Indians in Qatar. Indians constitute the largest segment of population in Qatar even more than the nationals. Qatar has been a success story for Indians but not without associated problems. The third paper by Rakhshanda F. Fazli and Rashid Aziz Faridi discusses the various aspects of return migrant's perceptions towards infrastructure, labour efficiency and Capital management in India. The fourth paper is by Jajati K. Patnaik and Chandan K. Panda. They have tried to assess the efficacy of consociationalism in Lebanon. The fifth paper by Fasih Raghbir Gauhar analyses the effectiveness of Jordan's diplomacy in dealing with regional crisis. The sixth paper by Azizur Rahman Azami offers a discussion on the Peshmerga women, the women wing of the Peshmerga, the Kurdish armed forces. The seventh paper by Atikur-Rahman deals with culture as a determinant in India-GCC relations. The eighth paper authored by Ziaur Rahman analyses the ideas of the Arab nation, Arab nationalism and pan Arab Unity.

The ninth paper by Syed Mohammad Raghieb is an effort to study the changing contours of India-Jordan relations. In the tenth paper Saddam Hussain and Nghma Farooqui have tried to study the Kurdish problem through the realist perspective. The eleventh paper by Saima Farhat studies the emerging trade nexus between India and United Arab Emirates before the Covid 19. The twelfth paper by Imtiaz Ahmad traces the historical and other dimensions of Yemeni diaspora. While Ankita Sanyal in her papers, thirteenth in line, studies Syrian women's attempt at state reconstruction since 2011. The fourteenth paper by Sana Noor and Haris Noor analyses the flow of FDI between India and the United Arab Emirates. The fifteenth paper by Alamgir Husain and Salina Akhtar studies Saudi Arabia's trade diplomacy specially in the context of India in the twenty first century. The sixteenth paper by Mohd Waseem and Haris Noor discusses the impact of Saudi Vision 2030 and the knowledge economy on non-Saudi workers. Further, there are two short papers included in the Notes and Discussions section. The paper by Sana Samreen analyses the usage of CHATGPT and its implications on the major oil exporting Countries of West Asia. While the paper by Shaik Sadiq Ulla Hussain analyses the opportunities and challenges of India-Qatar relations. This volume also includes a review of the book "Rethinking U.S. Education Policy: Paradigms of the Knowledge Economy" by Mohd Waseem. In my opinion the Journal of West Asian Studies has a lot to offer to the researcher and others interested in the West Asian region. I wish readers find this volume beneficial, interesting, insightful and useful for their academic pursuits and encourage them to consider this journal for publishing their valuable research. I express my sincere gratitude to all the anonymous reviewers for their valuable comments, suggestions and cooperation in ensuring the academic standard and timely publication of the Journals. I would be failing in my duty if I do not acknowledge the contributions of Associate editors Prof. Jawaid Iqbal and Prof. Rakhshanda Fazli. I am also thankful to the Vice-Chancellor of Aligarh Muslim University Prof. Mohd. Gulrez for his constant support and encouragement. Lastly I must acknowledge the dedicated support of the research scholars of the department, specially Mohd Waseem at every stage of the publication of this issue of the journal.

Muhammad Azher
Editor

**SAUDI VISION 2030 AND THE KNOWLEDGE ECONOMY:
IMPACT AND IMPLICATIONS FOR NON-SAUDI WORKERS**

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Abstract:

This research paper examines the impact and implications of Saudi Vision 2030 on non-Saudi workers in the context of the knowledge economy. Saudi Vision 2030 is an ambitious plan initiated by the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to diversify its economy and reduce its dependency on oil revenues. A vital component of this vision is the development of a knowledge-based economy that promotes innovation, research, and development. As the country moves towards this goal, examining the potential impact of the knowledge economy on non-Saudi workers is essential. This research paper explores the implications of Saudi Vision 2030 on non-Saudi workers in the context of the knowledge economy. It will discuss the opportunities and challenges faced by non-Saudi workers, analyse the government's policies and initiatives to attract and retain international talent and evaluate the potential long-term effects on the labour market and workforce composition. This research provides valuable insights for policymakers, stakeholders, and international professionals interested in understanding the impact of Saudi Vision 2030 on the labour market and knowledge economy.

Keywords: Knowledge Economy, Saudi Vision 2030, knowledge-based economy, Economic Diversification, ICT,

Introduction

The knowledge economy is an economic system in which the production and distribution of goods and services are based on knowledge and information. (Powell & Snellman, 2004) describe the knowledge economy as producing goods and services rooted in knowledge-intensive activities, facilitating rapid scientific and technical progress (p. 199). In the knowledge economy, the creation and dissemination of knowledge are key drivers of economic growth and innovation. The knowledge-based economy is an economy that depends on the production, distribution and use of knowledge and ICT (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) 1996). The knowledge economy has been a major factor in the development of many countries, and it is often associated with the rise of the service sector and the growth of the information and communication technology (ICT) industry. Economic prosperity gradually depends on the knowledgeable consumption of intangible assets, including knowledge, skills, and innovative potential, as the primary resource for gaining a financial advantage. The concept of "knowledge economy" describes the growing economic structure. (ESRC, 2005)

Peter Drucker framed the notion of a knowledge economy for the first time in his book "The Effective Executive" in 1966. The leading outline conformity in "The Effective Executive" was the manual and knowledge workers. A manual worker is a person whose job involves working with their hands and producing goods and services. On the other hand, a knowledge worker works like any labourer; they use their skills to have information and knowledge of a specific subject or sector. Knowledge Economy is to be understood as the modern phase of the evolution of the global economy. The concept of "Knowledge Economy" has been widely used over the last two decades. In the literature, various terms seem to be used synonymously: knowledge economy, knowledge-based economy, knowledge society, information society, digital society, knowledge-based society, etc.

Background

Saudi Arabia has long relied on oil revenues as the primary driver of its economy. However, recognising the need for diversification and sustainable economic growth, the Kingdom launched Saudi Vision 2030

in 2016. Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 is a transformative plan to diversify the country's economy and reduce its reliance on oil. The vision recognises the importance of transitioning to a knowledge-based economy to drive sustainable economic growth and create opportunities for the Saudi population. As part of this ambitious plan, Saudi Arabia seeks to attract and retain foreign talent to contribute to the development of the knowledge economy. A key pillar of this vision is the development of a knowledge-based economy, which involves harnessing innovation, research, and development to drive economic growth and enhance competitiveness in a globalised world. Non-Saudi workers are crucial in filling the skill gaps, transferring knowledge, and fostering innovation in various sectors.

Research Objectives

The primary objective of this research paper is to examine the impact of Saudi Vision 2030 on non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy. Specifically, it aims to:

- Explore the policies and initiatives implemented under Saudi Vision 2030 that affect non-Saudi workers.
- Investigate the employment opportunities available for non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy.
- Examine the skills development programs and integration efforts targeted at non-Saudi workers.
- Identify non-Saudi workers' challenges regarding employment and integration into the knowledge economy.

Significance of the Study

This research holds significant implications for policymakers, stakeholders, and international professionals interested in understanding the impact of Saudi Vision 2030 on non-Saudi workers and the broader knowledge economy. The findings will contribute to the existing knowledge on the subject and provide insights into the policies, opportunities, and challenges non-Saudi workers face. Moreover, the study's recommendations can inform future strategies to enhance the participation and integration of non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy, fostering a conducive environment for sustainable economic growth and development in Saudi Arabia.

Methodology

It primarily draws upon a comprehensive literature review, including academic articles, reports, government publications, and relevant case studies. The analysis will be conducted within the framework of a qualitative research approach, utilising a combination of thematic analysis and critical literature synthesis.

The paper will be organised as follows: Section 2 will provide an overview of Saudi Vision 2030 and its emphasis on the knowledge economy. Section 3 will examine the opportunities available to non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy, while Section 4 will discuss the challenges they face. Section 5 will delve into the government's policies and initiatives to attract and retain international talent. Section 6 will analyse the potential implications for the labour market and workforce composition. Section 7 will examine the Government Policies and Initiatives. Finally, Section 8 will present the conclusions, including a summary of findings, policy recommendations, and suggestions for future research.

Literature Review

A knowledge-based economy emphasises the central role of knowledge, innovation, and human capital in driving economic growth and competitiveness (Foray 2004.). It is characterised by the transition from traditional industries to those based on knowledge-intensive activities, such as research and development, technology adoption, and knowledge creation and dissemination (Dakhli 2004). Knowledge-based economies foster sustainable development by promoting creativity, entrepreneurship, and continuous learning (B.-Å. Lundvall 2010). Studies have highlighted the positive relationship between knowledge-based economies and indicators of economic performance, including productivity, GDP growth, and employment (Sveiby 1997). Smart development refers to integrating digital technologies, data analytics, and innovation to enhance economic, social, and environmental aspects of development (Caragliu 2011). It involves the use of smart infrastructure, the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), and advanced analytics to create efficient and sustainable systems (S. E. Bibri 2017). Smart development initiatives, such as smart cities, smart manufacturing, and smart agriculture, enable the efficient utilisation of resources, improve

service delivery, and drive economic competitiveness (Ahvenniemi 2017). Building a knowledge-based economy is not without challenges.

Moreover, the digital divide, data privacy concerns, and cybersecurity threats pose additional challenges to effectively implementing smart development initiatives (I. a. Lee 2015). However, strong institutional frameworks, supportive policies, Investment in human capital, public-private partnerships, and effective knowledge transfer mechanisms have been identified as critical factors for success in building knowledge-based economies (UNDP, 2020). South Korea's emphasis on research and development, human capital development, and technology adoption has contributed to its position as a global leader in innovation (J.-H. H. Lee 2018). These examples highlight the importance of coherent policy frameworks, strong public-private partnerships, and a long-term vision for building knowledge-based economies. For instance, Finland's "National Innovation System" emphasises industry, academia, and government collaboration to promote innovation and knowledge transfer (B.-Å. J. Lundvall 2009). Research institutions, such as universities and research centres, contribute to knowledge creation, technology transfer, and collaboration with industry (D. B. Audretsch 2018). A vibrant entrepreneurship ecosystem fosters innovation and the commercialisation of ideas, contributing to knowledge-based economies. Supporting startups, providing access to funding and mentorship, and creating favourable regulatory environments are critical aspects of nurturing entrepreneurship (D. B. Audretsch 2007).

The presence of incubators, accelerators, and technology parks facilitates collaboration, knowledge exchange, and networking among entrepreneurs, researchers, and investors (Mason 2014). A supportive cultural environment that values innovation, risk-taking, and continuous learning encourages entrepreneurship and creativity (D. B. Audretsch 2004). Additionally, social inclusivity and gender equality in education and employment opportunities contribute to a more diverse and dynamic knowledge-based economy (World Bank 2012). Developing digital skills in the workforce is crucial for leveraging smart technologies and driving a knowledge-based economy (Schwab 2015). Enhancing digital literacy, promoting lifelong learning, and upskilling the workforce in emerging technologies are essential for the successful adoption and utilisation of smart technologies (OECD, 2021). Open innovation models, which involve collaboration and knowledge sharing among organisations, have

gained prominence in knowledge-based economies (Chesbrough 2003). Smart development initiatives should consider environmental sustainability, resource efficiency, and climate change mitigation (S. E. Bibri 2018).

Saudi Vision 2030: The Path to a Knowledge Economy

Conceptual Framework: The knowledge economy refers to an economic system that produces, distributes, and utilises knowledge and information as primary drivers of economic growth. It emphasises the role of intellectual capital, innovation, and technology in creating value and generating competitive advantages. The knowledge economy encompasses various sectors such as information technology, research and development, education, healthcare, finance, and creative industries. Saudi Vision 2030 recognises the importance of transitioning to a knowledge-based economy as a key pillar of economic diversification and sustainable development. It aims to leverage Saudi Arabia's intellectual capital and human resources to drive innovation, enhance productivity, and foster a culture of lifelong learning. The vision focuses on developing strategic sectors, promoting entrepreneurship and innovation, and nurturing a knowledge-driven society.

The Knowledge Economy in Saudi Arabia: Saudi Arabia has recognised the potential of the knowledge economy in driving economic growth and reducing reliance on oil revenues. The country has invested significantly in education, research and development, and technology infrastructure to cultivate a conducive environment for knowledge-based industries. In recent years, Saudi Arabia has witnessed the emergence of several knowledge-intensive sectors, including information technology, telecommunications, finance, healthcare, and creative industries. These sectors have experienced substantial growth, attracting local and international investments, fostering entrepreneurship, and creating employment opportunities for Saudis and non-Saudis.

Saudi Vision 2030 and the Knowledge Economy: Saudi Vision 2030 provides a comprehensive framework for developing the knowledge economy in Saudi Arabia. The vision's strategic objectives and initiatives align with the knowledge economy principles, emphasising the importance of innovation, research and development, and human capital development.

Under Saudi Vision 2030, the government has implemented various policies and initiatives to support the growth of the knowledge economy. These include:

- Investment in research and development (R&D) infrastructure and establish research centres and innovation hubs.
- Promote digital transformation and adopt advanced technologies in e-commerce, fintech, and artificial intelligence sectors.
- To Enhance the education system to provide quality education and develop a skilled workforce focusing on science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) disciplines.
- Encourage entrepreneurship and establish startup ecosystems through funding, mentorship programs, and regulatory reforms.
- Promote knowledge-sharing and collaboration between academia, industry, and research institutions through partnerships and knowledge transfer initiatives.
- These efforts aim to attract and retain non-Saudi workers with specialised knowledge and expertise, foster a culture of innovation, and create an ecosystem supporting knowledge-intensive industries' growth.

Overall, Saudi Vision 2030 provides a strategic roadmap for building a thriving knowledge economy in Saudi Arabia. It offers opportunities for non-Saudi workers to contribute their skills and expertise while facilitating the country's economic transformation and diversification.

Opportunities for Non-Saudi Workers in the Knowledge Economy

Increased Demand for Skilled Professionals: As Saudi Arabia endeavours to build a knowledge-based economy, there is a growing demand for skilled professionals with expertise in various fields. Non-Saudi workers with specialised knowledge, advanced technical skills, and experience in technology, research, engineering, finance, and healthcare can find ample opportunities in the Kingdom. They are expanding sectors such as information technology, renewable energy, and healthcare, presenting avenues for non-Saudi workers to contribute their expertise and fill skill gaps.

Entrepreneurial Opportunities: Saudi Vision 2030 places significant emphasis on fostering entrepreneurship and supporting the growth of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). Non-Saudi workers with

entrepreneurial aspirations can exploit this focus by establishing businesses or partnering with Saudi entrepreneurs. The government has implemented initiatives such as venture capital funds, incubators, and accelerators to support, fund, and mentorship for startups. Non-Saudi workers with innovative ideas and business acumen can drive entrepreneurship and innovation in the knowledge economy.

Research and Development Collaborations: Saudi Arabia actively seeks to enhance its research and development capabilities through collaborations with international institutions and experts. Non-Saudi researchers and academics can engage in joint research projects, collaborate with Saudi universities and research centres, and contribute to scientific advancements in various fields. These collaborations offer opportunities for non-Saudi workers to contribute their expertise, expand their networks, and participate in cutting-edge research that can have a global impact.

Foreign Direct Investment and Job Creation: Saudi Vision 2030 aims to attract foreign direct investment (FDI) to stimulate economic growth and diversification. As international companies invest in Saudi Arabia and establish operations in the knowledge economy sectors, non-Saudi workers can find employment opportunities within these organisations. The presence of multinational companies and the establishment of new industries can create a demand for skilled professionals in areas such as management, technology, marketing, and research. Non-Saudi workers with the required qualifications and experience can benefit from the job creation resulting from FDI inflows.

It is important to note that while opportunities exist for non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy, specific requirements and regulations govern their employment. These may include obtaining work visas, meeting specific skill and qualification criteria, and complying with labour laws and regulations. Awareness of these requirements and adherence to the relevant processes are crucial for non-Saudi workers to access and maximise the opportunities available in the Kingdom's knowledge economy.

Challenges Faced by Non-Saudi Workers in the Knowledge Economy

Cultural and Social Factors: Non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy may face cultural and social integration challenges. Saudi Arabia has a unique cultural and social fabric, and adapting to local

customs, traditions, and norms can be a significant adjustment for non-Saudi workers. Language barriers, different work styles, and unfamiliar social dynamics may pose challenges to effective communication and collaboration in the workplace. Building relationships, understanding cultural nuances, and navigating social interactions can be essential for non-Saudi workers to thrive in the knowledge economy.

Legal and Administrative Barriers: Non-Saudi workers may encounter legal and administrative barriers when working in the knowledge economy. Obtaining work visas and residence permits and complying with immigration regulations can be complex and time-consuming. Specific requirements and restrictions on employment in certain sectors may impact non-Saudi workers' ability to pursue their desired career paths. Adherence to labour laws, employment contracts, and legal procedures can also present challenges for non-Saudi workers, requiring them to navigate the legal landscape effectively.

Language and Communication Challenges: Proficiency in Arabic is often required for many jobs in the knowledge economy, particularly those involving interactions with local stakeholders. Non-Saudi workers who are not fluent in Arabic may face challenges communicating effectively with colleagues, clients, and government officials. Language barriers can impede collaboration, hinder productivity, and limit career advancement opportunities. While English is commonly used in the business environment, having a working knowledge of Arabic can enhance the ability to integrate and succeed in the Saudi workforce.

Workforce Localization Policies: Saudi Arabia has implemented workforce localisation policies to increase employment opportunities for Saudi nationals. These policies prioritise the hiring and development of Saudi talent in specific sectors and job roles. Non-Saudi workers may face challenges navigating these policies and meeting the localisation requirements. Implementing quotas, limitations on specific job roles, and preferences given to Saudi nationals can limit employment opportunities for non-Saudi workers. Adapting to the evolving workforce localisation policies and finding ways to contribute to Saudi talent development can be crucial for non-Saudi workers to overcome these challenges.

Non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy must know these challenges and develop strategies to address them. This may involve investing in language and cultural training, seeking mentorship and support networks, staying updated on legal and administrative

requirements, and proactively engaging with local communities to foster relationships and understanding. Collaboration between government authorities, employers, and non-Saudi workers is essential to create an environment supporting international talent's integration and success in the knowledge economy.

Government Policies and Initiatives

National Transformation Program and Foreign Workforce Regulations: As part of Saudi Vision 2030, the government has implemented the National Transformation Program (NTP) to drive economic diversification and develop the knowledge economy. The NTP includes initiatives to regulate and manage the foreign workforce per the country's economic objectives. The government has introduced various regulations and reforms to streamline visa processes, improve labour market flexibility, and enhance the rights and protections of workers, including non-Saudi workers. These policies aim to create a conducive environment for international talent to contribute to the knowledge economy.

Visa Reforms and Attracting International Talent: The government has introduced visa reforms and initiatives to attract and retain international talent. For example, the "Quality of Life" program offers long-term residency visas for non-Saudi workers, providing stability and security. The "Privileged Iqama" program allows eligible expatriates to obtain extended residency and work rights, providing greater flexibility and ease of business. Furthermore, the government has established the "Saudi Investment Residency Program" to attract foreign investors and entrepreneurs. These initiatives signal the government's commitment to welcoming and valuing non-Saudi workers as contributors to the knowledge economy.

Educational and Skills Development Programs: The government has implemented academic and skills development programs to support the development of a skilled workforce. The "Quality Education" program focuses on improving the quality of education at all levels, from primary to tertiary. Saudi universities are encouraged to collaborate with international institutions to enhance their curriculum and research capabilities. Additionally, vocational training programs are being expanded to equip Saudi nationals and non-Saudi workers with the necessary skills for the knowledge economy. These initiatives aim to enhance the talent pool and bridge skill gaps in the labour market.

Support for Entrepreneurship and Innovation: The government has launched several initiatives to support entrepreneurship and innovation in the knowledge economy. The "Misk Innovation" program provides funding, mentorship, and support for startups and entrepreneurs, both Saudi and non-Saudi. Business incubators and accelerators have been established to facilitate the growth of SMEs and foster an entrepreneurial ecosystem. Furthermore, the government has created venture capital funds and investment incentives to attract local and international investors. These initiatives enable non-Saudi workers to start businesses, contribute to innovation, and drive economic growth.

The government's policies and initiatives demonstrate a commitment to attracting, retaining, and supporting non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy. By streamlining visa processes, improving education and skills development programs, and fostering entrepreneurship and innovation, the government aims to create a favourable environment for international talent to thrive and contribute to Saudi Arabia's economic diversification goals. Continuous evaluation and refinement of these policies will be crucial to ensure their effectiveness and alignment with the evolving needs of the knowledge economy.

Implications for the Labor Market and Workforce Composition

Impact on Skilled Migration Patterns: Developing a knowledge economy in Saudi Arabia can attract skilled professionals worldwide. As the demand for specialised expertise grows, non-Saudi workers may play a significant role in filling skill gaps and contributing to developing key sectors. This influx of international talent can lead to a more diverse and multicultural workforce, bringing different perspectives, experiences, and knowledge to the labour market. However, it is important to balance recruiting non-Saudi workers to develop local talent and ensure opportunities for Saudi nationals.

Potential Effects on Wage Structures: Non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy can affect wage structures. Highly skilled non-Saudi workers may command higher salaries due to their expertise and the demand for their skills. This can potentially impact wage levels within the industry and influence salary expectations for Saudi and non-Saudi workers. The government and employers need to monitor and manage wage structures to ensure fair compensation practices and maintain the competitiveness of the labour market.

Workforce Diversity and Inclusion: The influx of non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy can contribute to greater workforce diversity and inclusion. A diverse workforce brings together individuals from different cultural backgrounds, experiences, and perspectives, fostering innovation and creativity. It also enhances cross-cultural understanding and promotes a more inclusive work environment. Embracing diversity and implementing inclusive practices can improve collaboration, productivity, and employee satisfaction in the knowledge economy.

Skill Transfer and Knowledge Exchange: The presence of non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy allows skill transfer and knowledge exchange. International professionals bring expertise, best practices, and innovative ideas from their countries. This knowledge exchange can enrich the local workforce, enhance the skills of Saudi nationals, and contribute to the overall development of the knowledge economy. Encouraging collaboration, networking, and mentorship programs can facilitate the transfer of skills and knowledge between non-Saudi workers and their Saudi counterparts.

The implications for the knowledge economy's labour market and workforce composition are multifaceted. While including non-Saudi workers brings benefits such as addressing skill gaps and promoting diversity, it also requires careful management to develop local talent and preserve fair labour practices. Striking the right balance between international talent and local workforce development is essential for the long-term success and sustainability of the knowledge economy.

Government Policies and Initiatives

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Educational and Skills Development Programs: The government has implemented academic and skills development programs to support the development of a skilled workforce. The "Quality Education" program focuses on improving the quality of education at all levels, from primary to tertiary. Saudi universities are encouraged to collaborate with international institutions to enhance their curriculum and research capabilities. Additionally, vocational training programs are being expanded to equip Saudi nationals and non-Saudi workers with the necessary skills for the knowledge economy. These initiatives aim to enhance the talent pool and bridge skill gaps in the labour market.

Support for Entrepreneurship and Innovation: The government has launched several initiatives to support entrepreneurship and innovation in the knowledge economy. The "Misk Innovation" program provides funding, mentorship, and support for startups and entrepreneurs, both Saudi and non-Saudi. Business incubators and accelerators have been established to facilitate the growth of SMEs and foster an entrepreneurial ecosystem. Furthermore, the government has created venture capital funds and investment incentives to attract local and international investors. These initiatives enable non-Saudi workers to start businesses, contribute to innovation, and drive economic growth.

The government's policies and initiatives demonstrate a commitment to attracting, retaining, and supporting non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy. By streamlining visa processes, improving education and skills development programs, and fostering entrepreneurship and innovation, the government aims to create a favourable environment for international talent to thrive and contribute to Saudi Arabia's economic

diversification goals. Continuous evaluation and refinement of these policies will be crucial to ensure their effectiveness and alignment with the evolving needs of the knowledge economy.

Conclusion

Saudi Vision 2030's focus on developing a knowledge-based economy has significant implications for non-Saudi workers. The opportunities available in sectors such as technology, research, entrepreneurship, and foreign direct investment present avenues for international talent to contribute their expertise and skills. However, non-Saudi workers also face challenges related to cultural integration, legal and administrative barriers, language and communication, and workforce localisation policies. The Saudi government has implemented various policies and initiatives to address these challenges. These include visa reforms, educational and skills development programs, and support for entrepreneurship and innovation. These efforts aim to attract, retain, and support non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy, ensuring their successful integration and maximising their contributions.

The development of the knowledge economy and the influx of non-Saudi workers have implications for the labour market and workforce composition. Skilled migration patterns may change, leading to a more diverse and multicultural workforce. International talent may influence wage structures, requiring careful monitoring and management. Workforce diversity and inclusion can be enhanced, fostering innovation and collaboration. Skill transfer and knowledge exchange between non-Saudi workers and Saudi nationals can contribute to the overall development of the knowledge economy. Saudi Vision 2030 presents opportunities for non-Saudi workers in the knowledge economy; addressing their challenges is crucial and ensures a supportive and inclusive environment. By leveraging the expertise and contributions of international talent, Saudi Arabia can accelerate its economic diversification, drive innovation, and achieve sustainable growth in line with its vision for 2030. Continued evaluation, adaptation, and implementation of policies and initiatives will be essential to foster the successful integration of non-Saudi workers and harness their full potential in the knowledge economy.

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